

Credit Appraisal of Home Loan Finance

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Abstract:

In today's fast paced business environment, banks operating in retail space require a change resilient vertically integrated value chain for delivering the most competitive products and services. This need is redefining the boundaries of a banks value chain creating greater thrust for this value add, right from the lowest end of the delivery channels. In the loans and advances product space, this requires an integration strategy right from Sourcing, Evaluation and Servicing to Collections, Recoveries and Write-Off Management. This research paper elaborate the delivery capability of a bank, operating in home loans space which is faced with challenges of rapid changing products and business processes and also to handle large transaction volume handling due to high business volumes.

This research paper has been conducted in Union Bank of India which deals with Home loan financing. The core theme of the research paper is based on study and analysis of Home Loan schemes, documentation & sanctioning procedure of Union Bank of India. Indian banking is booming sector in India. Banks have been upgrading and innovative technology day to day for delivering products and services through various innovative channels. To ensure the competitive edge in future, banks have to evolve new approaches, improve product to keep pace with ever-changing and growing expectations of customers. Today's world banks have to fight with rivals in terms of quality of their services.

Keywords:Banking, Home Finance, Disbursement, Home Loan schemes

1. INTRODUCTION

Banking in India originated in the first decade of 18th century. The first banks were The General Bank of India, which started in 1786, and Bank of Hindustan, both of which are now defunct. The oldest bank in existence in India is the State Bank of India, which originated in the "The Bank of Bengal" in Calcutta in June 1806. This was one of the three presidency banks, the other two being the Bank of Bombay and the Bank of Madras. The presidency banks were established under charters from the British East India Company. They merged in 1925 to form the Imperial Bank of India, which, upon India's independence, became the State Bank of India. For many years the Presidency banks acted as quasi-central banks, as did their successors. The Reserve Bank of India formally took on the responsibility of regulating the Indian banking sector from 1935. After India's independence in 1947, the Reserve Bank was nationalized and given broader powers.

By the 1960s, the Indian banking industry has become an important tool to facilitate the development of the Indian economy. At the same time, it has emerged as a large employer, and a debate has ensued about the possibility to nationalize the banking industry. Indira Gandhi, the-then Prime Minister of India expressed the intention of the GOI in the annual conference of the All India Congress Meeting in a paper entitled "Stray thoughts on Bank Nationalization."

The paper was received with positive enthusiasm. Thereafter, her move was swift and sudden, and the GOI issued an ordinance and nationalized the 14 largest commercial banks with effect from the midnight of July 19, 1969. Mr. Jayaprakash Narayan, a national leader of India, described the step as a "masterstroke of political sagacity." Within two weeks of the issue of the ordinance, the Parliament passed the Banking Companies (Acquisition and Transfer of Undertaking) Bill, and it received the presidential approval on 9th August, 1969.\

2. OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

1. To study the appraisal process of home loan proposal
2. To understand the process and key issues in sanctions
3. To study the restricted areas of credit of Bank
4. To understand and analyse the performance of the Bank regarding sanction, disbursement.
5. To know the documentation process for home loan procedure

3. LIMITATIONS

Following are the limitations for carrying out this research paperwork:

1. Credit appraisal system includes various types of detail studies for different areas of analysis, but due to time constraint, analysis was of limited areas only.
2. As the credit appraisal is one of the crucial areas for any bank, some of the Technicalities are not revealed.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

MEANING OF RESEARCH

- Research is a scientific and systematic search for pertinent information on a specific topic. Research means search for knowledge. It is discovery of facts, developments of facts and verification of facts.
- It is an attempt to find practical solutions to the problems with the help of application of scientific methods.
- The purpose of research is to discover the answers of questions through application of scientific procedure.
- The aim of research is to find out the truth.

• RESEARCH DESIGN:

Analytical in nature.

• DATA COLLECTION:

Data collecting is collecting information for research paper while studying a business through different sources of data collection. It is very important aspect of any investigation. The research methodology includes methods of data collection. Data collection process begins after research problem has been defined & research plan checked out while deciding about method of data collection to be used for studies. There are two methods of data collection as follows:

1. Primary Data:

The first-hand information bearing on any research which has been collected by the researcher may be called “primary data”. Collected information with the help of proposals of credit policy sanctioned by the Bank.

2. Secondary Data:

The Secondary Data on the other hand, are based on second-hand information. The data which have been already been collected, compiled & presented easier by any agency may be used for the purpose of investigation such data may be called “Secondary Data”. Collecting the information with the help of Annual Reports, Magazines, Internet, and Reference Book. The Secondary data was provided by organization. The needed information was collected from Journals, Annual Reports, Magazines, Website, and Data at UBI etc.

5. DATA ANALYSIS WITH THE HELP OF CASE STUDIES

Points	UBI	MERCHANT BANK
Sector	Public Sector	Private Sector
Door Step Service	Not Provide	Provide
Mortgage	Registered Mortgage	Oral / Equitable Mortgage
Guarantor	Mandatory and salaried	Mandatory
Approved Research paperFile	Not Carried	Process Carried
Administrative Fees	0.5%+ Service Tax@12.36%	0.5%+Service Tax@12.36%
Documentation	Lengthy	Easy
Dependents	Max.5 Nos.	Max.5 Nos.
Increase or Decrease in	Not Possible	Possible

Loan Amount		
Age limit	70 years	No limit
Deduping	Not Carried	Process Carried
CIBIL Verification	Mandatory	Mandatory
Minimum Gross Income		
No. of Yrs in Employment	3 Yrs	3 Yrs
Part Prepayment Fees	Nil	Nil
FULL PREPAYMENT FEES	Nil	2.00% on Outstanding +ST@12.36%
Max Tenor	20 Yrs	20 Yrs
Age Norms	Min. 21 yrs at loan origination Max.70 yrs or age of retirement, whichever is less at loan maturity.	Min. 21 yrs at loan origination Max- No Limit.
Borrowers	All owners to be Borrowers	All owners to be Borrowers
Points	Union Bank of India	HDFC Bank
Sanction Validity	6 months	6 months for Salaried & 3 months for SEP/SENP
Property Identification	Mandatory	Mandatory

<p>Calculation of Loan Eligibility</p>	<p>For Salaried- (A)</p> <p>a. Gross Salary x 12 x 4</p> <p>b. Net Salary x 12 x 5</p> <p>(B) 60:40 Ratio</p> <p>Gross Income / 12 x 60% - Obligation = Eligible EMI</p> <p>For SENP-</p> <p>1) Total Income x 4</p> <p>2) Net Taxable Income x 5</p> <p>Whichever is higher in above 1) & 2)</p>	<p>As per Applicable FOIR - Salaried</p> <p>5500- <8000 =40%</p> <p>8000- <20000 =45%</p> <p>20000-<25000 =50%</p> <p>>=25000 =55%</p> <p>(Discretion of 2% will be allowed higher than the approved limits)</p> <p>FOR SENP- MAX.55%</p>
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Competitors Of Union Bank Of India

- State bank of india
- Bank of india
- Icici bank

TABLE: CASE I AND CASE II COMPARISION

	CASE I	CASE II
EMPLOYMENT	Salaried	Self-employed
LOAN PROPOSAL	4,00,000	36,00,000
TENURE	120 months	120 months
INTEREST RATE	13%	13.25%
EMI	7,700	33,975
REASON	Flat purchase	Flat purchase

ANALYSIS :

1. The borrower in 1st case is a salaried person where his requirement for home loan is quite low as compared to case II, who is a businessman
2. The rate of Interest is fixed in KUCB but in the above cases the rate of interest differs as the proposals are bought at different periods.
3. The EMI contains the principal amount and the interest on borrowings. Hence, in 1st case the EMI

• LOAN AMOUNT

- **INTERPRETATION 1 –**

The above graph shows the amount of loan disbursed by the bank:

Case-1 - 4,00,000

Case-2 – 36,00,00

Case-3 – 19,00,000

Case-4 – 10,00,000

The loans are sanctioned as per the eligibility and criteria. The number of applications in bank and the number of cases disbursed varies because all cases that enter into bank are not disbursed. The customer may be Employed or self-employed and the reasons for applying for home loan also vary from customer to customer.

In the above graph we can see the range of loan amounts that the bank has disbursed according to the criteria. Case 1 is a salaried person who requires funds to purchase a flat Rs. 4000, Case 2 is a self-employed person who requires funds to purchase a flat, Case 3 is a self-employed person who requires funds for construction purpose, and Case 4 is a salaried person who requires funds for construction purpose.

- **REDUCING EMI RATES AS PER EACH CASES**

ALL THE ABOVE CASES HAVE REDUCING EMI METHOD WHERE THE

• RATE OF INTEREST

• TENURE

❖ INTERPRETATION

From above cases we come to know that how home loan is required by the customer for several reasons and the entire process of home loan which is usually done in three stages i.e.

1. Pre-sanction stage
2. Sanction stage
3. Disbursement stage

These steps help to better understand the Home loan process of co-operative banks and study in detail the reasons of Home Loan requirement.

6. FINDINGS

1. Credit appraisal of home loan is done to check the commercial, financial & technical viability of the research paper proposed its funding pattern & further checks the primary or collateral security cover available for the recovery of such funds
2. Credit & risk go hand in hand
3. The UNION BANK OF INDIA need to innovate their delivery platforms by using Internet banking, mobile banking and card-based platforms for delivery of transaction-banking as well as credit products, and enhance the service element.
4. ATM facility is the vast used technology by the general public. Bank contains only limited ATM's which create hurdles while transacting easily .They look for convenience and simplicity in their banking requirements and banks should deliver these through an effective use of technology.
5. The Bank should keep on revising its Credit Policy which will help Bank's effort to correct the course of the policies
6. In the business world risk arises out of:-
7. Uncertainties in the business environment
8. Weakness in the financial positions of the customers
9. A banker's task is to identify/assess the risk factors/parameters & manage/mitigate them on continuous basis

10. The Credit Appraisal process adopted by the bank take into account all possible factors which go into appraising the risk associated with a loan

7. CONCLUSION

Finance management is the backbone of any organizations and hence yields a number of job options ranging from strategic financial planning to sales. From the study of Credit appraisal of Home loan finance, it can be concluded that credit appraisal of home loan should therefore be based on the following factors; the same are applied at the Bank Branches:

- Financial performance
- Business performance
- Quality of management
- Conduct of account

Loan policy contains various norms for sanction of Home loans. Bank Norms for providing home loans are flexible & it may differ from case to case. Usually, it is seen that credit appraisal is basically done on the basis of fundamental soundness. But, after different types of case studies, our conclusion was such that credit appraisal system is not only looking for financial wealth. Other strong parameters also play an important role in analysing credit worthiness of the customers. In all, the viability of the research paper from every aspect is analysed, as well as type of business, promoters, customers and their past records, also plays crucial role in increasing chances of getting research paper approved for.